

IMPROVEMENT IN THE IMPACT ENERGY ABSORPTION OF RECYCLED CFRP

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SUMMARY

We developed recycled CFRTP by using waste CFRP for secondary structural parts of current automobile. A possibility that impact energy absorption of CFRTP would be improved by the optimization of crush process of the waste CFRP and the addition of an aramid fiber to the CFRTP was examined.

Keywords: CFRP, CFRTP, Recycle, impact energy absorption, Aramid, Automobile

INTRODUCTION

The world energy consumption continues to increase yearly. Especially, sectional energy consumption of transport sector has been increasing firmly and too much depended on oil for a long time. It is necessary for us to develop the effective measures as soon as possible. Although fuel cell technology is now under development, it takes much time to be practical application. Therefore, we have focused on lightening the weight of automobile by using CFRP (carbon fiber reinforced plastics) [1-4]. CFRP is used for the aircraft or space field since their high specific strength, specific rigidity and lightweight. However current CFRP is not suitable because of high cost, long manufacturing time and the difficulty of secondary processing and recycling [5]. To reduce energy consumption and cost of CFRP manufacturing, reuse of carbon fiber is the most effective [6,7].

In this paper we investigated recyclability of CFRP, and focused on establishment of recycling with crushed CFRTP (carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics), because it is proper to mass production, cheap and easy to be recycled.

As a method of CFRP recycling, in the future, the injection molding method by crushed CFRP with thermoplastics is adapted to obtain the recycled material at lower cost and higher manufacturing speed. The problem in recycle by crushed CFRP with the injection molding method is the declining of mechanical properties due to fibers getting short [8,9]. As the thermoplastics PP (polypropylene) is used in this study because of

material cost and recyclability. However, with the poor adhesion of PP and short length of fibers, the impact energy absorption of the recycled CFRTP is insufficient for automobile structures. Figure 1 shows the flexural property of the three points bending test and the Izod impact energy absorption of the recycled CFRTP with the injection molding method [10]. The size of the flexural test specimens were length 80 mm * width 15 mm * thickness 3 mm. Five times tests were performed for every condition; thermoplastics without CF, longitudinal (L) and transversal (T) specimens for injection direction of CFRTP with $V_f = 7, 15, 24$ and 30 % of recycled CF. As shown in Fig.1, the flexural modulus of longitudinal direction became large almost in proportion to the fiber volume fraction, however those of transversal direction and Izod impact energy absorption showed low and almost constant regardless of fiber volume fraction. Additionally, in case of the Izod impact energy absorption test, energy absorption ability fell down drastically due to the mixture of CF in thermoplastics.

From such a background, the objective of this study is to improve the mechanical properties of recycled CFRTP by optimizing the pre-treatment of the crushed CFRP before molding. Furthermore, we evaluate the effect of adding aramid fiber to crushed CFRP. The reason of the usage of the aramid fiber is its characteristic mechanical properties. Therefore, the aramid fiber is expected to support the poor impact energy absorption ability of recycled CFRTP when aramid fiber is compounded with recycled CFRP.

Figure 1 Flexural properties of the recycled CF/PP with different V_f

Recycle Method in This Study

Recycle Method

As a method of CFRP recycling, heat recovery and material recycling have been investigated, and material recycling is better from a viewpoint of LCA (life cycle assessment) since carbon fiber should be reused as not just carbon but carbon fiber[6, 7]. Furthermore, considering that the cost of recycled CFRP must be very cheap, establishment of the recycling technology of CFRP will drastically contribute to lower-pricing of CFRP products. Hence, the recycling technology of CFRP is indispensable in the mass-production application, in especially passenger automobile, to contribute global energy saving.

As a method of taking out carbon fiber from waste CFRP, evaporation [11] and a chemical depolymerization of thermosetting resin [12] are reported as shown in fig. 2. In this paper, the crushed CFRP (T700S ; PAN based carbon fiber with epoxy resin) and PP (J3000GP ; produced by CALP Co. LTD., Japan) resin was investigated to obtain the recycled CFRTTP at lower cost, and the press molding method was used to make a variety of kinds of samples for trial purposes. According to these methods, there is a possibility that a high performance recycled material can be molded with a press molding because long carbon fiber is taken out.

Figure 2 Recycling method of Carbon fiber

Molding CFRTTP Specimens

Wasted CFRP was crushed by machine into square of about 1 cm, and classified into three groups by size. Figure 3 shows crushed CFRP of small size and medium size. As for crushed CFRP of middle size, the fiber length is not only long but also the lump size is large. Therefore the crushed CFRP of medium size was fibrillated by dividing in detail by the hand work. The width of fibrillated CFRP became narrow without shorten the length of fiber (see Fig. 4).

These crushed CFRPs and resin were dried well, and kneaded with PP by two-axis mixing machine to make carbon fiber volume fraction be 15%. Laboprastomil (Toyo Seiki Seisaku-Sho., Ltd., 10C100 R60) was used for the mixing. The mixing condition

was 200 degree Celsius, 10 rpm, and 5 minutes. Besides, for improvement of adhesibility, maleic acid was added at the mixing process. Next, the press molding was done by using hot press machine. The molding temperature was 200 degree Celsius, and the size of the molded board was 130mm × 100mm × 4mm. Finally, the molded boards were cut out for test pieces with a diamond cutter. The size of the test pieces of the three points bending test were 70mm × 15mm × 4mm and those of the Izod impact test were 90mm × 10mm × 4mm.

Figure 3 Photo of Crushed CFRP grouped into three classes by size

Figure 4 Closeup of the crushed CFRP and fibrillated CFRP

Results of Recycled CFRTTP from crushed CFRP

Experimental Results and Discussions

The three points bending test was performed under the condition that cross head speed was 2mm/min and support span was 64mm at room temperature. The Izod impact test was performed under the condition that hammer load was 26.8kgf and span was 395mm.

The test was done 5 times for each material respectively. Figure 5 shows the results of the three points bending test and the Izod impact test of recycled CFRTP from various shapes of crushed CFRP.

In the comparison of the small size and the medium size, as for both flexure tests and the Izod impact test, significant difference was not seen. However, the value of flexural modulus and flexural strength of the fibrillated was much higher than the results of others. The reason might be that adhesive property with carbon fiber and PP having improved by fibrillation (see Fig. 6).

Figure 5 Results of three points bending test and Izod impact test of recycled CFRTP from various shape of crushed CFRP

Figure 6 SEM photographs of fracture cross section (Small size, Medium size, fibrillated)

PRETREATMENT OF CRUSHED CFRP BY HEATING

Pretreatment

The method of removing epoxy resin by pretreatment to fibrillate the CFRP efficiently was attempted. The crushed CFRP was heated at 500 degree Celsius in an air for 10 to 60 minutes by electric furnace before kneading. It aims to fibrillate the CFRP without shortening the length of fiber by removing epoxy resin. Depending on treatment time, there are some different states of the rate by which epoxy resin is removed. Figure 7 shows the epoxy resin was removed rapidly in the fast 20 minutes. The recycled CFRTTP from crushed CFRP with heat treatment were molded with the result of Fig. 7 so that the volume fraction of carbon fiber might become 15%.

Figure 7 Influence of heating time on remove rate of epoxy resin for the crushed CFRP

Figure 8 SEM photographs at surface of crushed CFRP with heat treatment.

Experimental Results and Discussions

Figure 9 shows result of the three points bending test and the Izod impact test of recycled CFRTP with heat treatment. The test method was similar to the above-mentioned. The flexural modulus and the flexural strength first increased with heating time, greatest in an area for from 40 to 50 minutes, and then decreased for 60 minutes. As for the Izod impact absorption, almost the same improvement was seen in all the processing time.

Figure 9 Results of three points bending test and Izod impact test of recycled CFRTP from crushed CFRP with heat treatment.

IMPROVEMENT BY ADDITION OF THE ARAMID FIBER TO RECYCLED CFRTP

This chapter describes the addition of the aramid fiber to the CFRTP. The aramid fiber is expected to support the poor impact energy absorption ability of recycled CFRTP when the aramid fiber is compounded with recycled CFRP.

Figure 10 shows influence of the V_f of AF/PP (aramid fiber/polypropylene) and recycled CFRTP in three points bending test and Izod impact test, where the number means V_f . The AF/PP was made from the fresh aramid fiber (Teijin T322EH, $L = 4.5\text{mm}$). Even if V_f increases, only the Izod impact energy absorption of CFRTP is remaining low.

The effects of the addition of an aramid fiber to the CFRTP are summarized in Fig. 11.

The all values of flexural modulus, strength and Izod impact energy absorption were increased by the addition of an aramid fiber. Especially, Izod impact energy absorption

has improved greatly by the effect of the property of the aramid fiber. In addition, a hybrid effect can be confirmed about flexural property when comparing it with same Vf. For instance, in the comparison between the values of CF10%/AF5% and the AF15%/PP and the CF15%/PP, the modulus was a performance of CF15%/PP, the strength was a performance of AF15%/PP, and the performance in both good one appeared.

The Izod impact energy absorption of AF10% decreased with an increase in CF volume. This means that the impact energy absorption ability of recycled CFRTP will be improved by the addition of proper amount of aramid fiber.

Figure 10 Influence of Vf of AF/PP from fresh aramid fiber and crushed CFRP on three points bending test and Izod impact test.

Figure 11 The effects of the addition of an aramid fiber to the CFRTP on three points bending test and Izod impact test of recycled CFRTP from crushed CFRP.

CONCLUSIONS

To develop the recycled CFRTP by using waste CFRP for secondary structural parts of current automobile. We tried to improve the poor impact energy absorption ability of recycled CFRP by the optimization of crush process with treatment of the waste CFRP and the addition of an aramid fiber to the CFRTP. Then we confirmed that the impact energy absorption of the recycled CFRTP was improved by optimization in the shape of crushed CFRP with long fibrillate fiber, and improved greatly by adding a little aramid fiber to the polymer. Furthermore, the flexural modulus, strength were increased by the addition of an aramid fiber. Especially, a hybrid effect can be confirmed about flexural strength when comparing it with same volume fraction of fiber. Of course, there are a lot of parameters to study for a practical application; we showed that there are proper volume fractions of aramid fiber in this study.

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